

Analysis of Bandwidth Allocation Models Reconfiguration Impacts

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Abstract

Bandwidth Allocation Models (BAMs) are configured in MPLS/ DS-TE networks by setting Bandwidth Constraints (BCs) for traffic classes. Effectively, BAMs define how bandwidth (resource) is used and shared by network applications. Proposed BAMs like MAM - Maximum Allocation Model, RDM - Russian Dolls Model, G-RDM - Generalized RDM and AllocTC-Sharing aim to optimize the use of bandwidth for links with different bandwidth allocation characteristics and sharing. As such, the adoption of different BAMs and/or changes in the traffic profile may result in different traffic allocation patterns and distinct operational behaviors for the network. This article analyses the impact of BAM reconfiguration in relation to network parameters and characteristics such as link utilization, preemptions and flow blocking for different traffic scenarios. Authors argue that the creation of a mechanism for smoothing the BAMs reconfiguration process may result in benefits for network operation in terms of flow preemption and / or blocking.

Keywords — BAM, Dynamic Network Management, MAM, RDM, AllocTC-Sharing, BAM Reconfiguration

1 Introduction and Motivation

Bandwidth Allocation Models (BAMs) are used by network managers in MPLS / DS-TE networks by configuring Bandwidth Constraints (BCs) for the purpose of defining rules and limits for bandwidth utilization by traffic classes (TCs) (set of applications) (F. Le Faucheur, 2005b) . These models effectively defined as bandwidth (resource) are obtained and shared by applications.

The BAM configuration for models like MAM, RDM, RDM-G and AllocTC-Sharing, among others, depends of a network traffic evaluation process typically done by the network manager. This evaluation process considers aspects such as the set of applications mapped to specific traffic classes (TC), the priorities assigned to each traffic class (TC) and defined application SLAs (Service Level Agreements) and QoS (Quality of Service) parameters.

Once a specific BAM is setup and configured for the network, it will typically have a static and optimized behavior in relation to link utilization, preemptions and blocked LSPs. In brief, configuration assumes a “traffic profile” and results in a “network behavior pattern”.

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In most cases, the evaluation and selection of BAM to be used in a network is a complex process and network managers often re-evaluate their choice in case of network problem and/or need of further optimization (Jennings, 2007) (Strassner, 2009) (Samaan, 2009). As such, the evaluation of bandwidth allocation models configuration could be eventually made by an autonomic framework capable of analyzing the network current state and its requirements (SLA/QoS). Based on this evaluation, the autonomic framework may infer the most appropriate BAM and adequate configuration. A proposal for a framework with autonomic features considering the BAM switching and optimization context presented is discussed in Reale (2013).

This paper main motivation is to investigate the impact of BAM on-the-fly bandwidth constraints (BCs) reconfiguration in DS-TE networks. The main focus is to identify advantages, disadvantages and challenges while reconfiguring BAMs under different traffic scenarios.

In order to develop a management analysis scenario it is proposed that two basic management approaches could be used for BC reconfiguration: the Hard Approach and the Soft Approach.

The Hard Approach (HA) management premise is to reconfigure the network mandatorily. In other words, the HA management approach assumes that the network is supposed to be reconfigured immediately, independently of its current state and assumes any consequences to applications and related traffic. As such, switching with HA approach may lead to hurting BAM principles and get negative impacts on network parameters like preemption.

The Soft Approach (SA) management premise is to reconfigure the network smoothly. In doing that, the SA management approach preserves BAM principles and enforces the reduction of negative impacts on network evaluation parameters.

This article is organized as follows: we start with a brief analysis of most currently used and discussed BAMs (MAM, RDM, G-RDM and AllocTC-Sharing) in relation to BCs reconfiguration. Following that, we analyze the Hard and Soft management approaches using simulation, in order to investigate the impacts of on-the-fly BAM reconfiguration.

2 Bandwidth Allocation Models (BAMs) - A Brief Overview

The state of the art of the bandwidth allocation models is focused on the research for new models with different strategies for allocation and resource sharing (Adami, 2007) (Le Faucheur, 2005a) (Le Faucheur, 2005c) (Reale, 2012) (Tong, 2007) (Pinto Neto, 2008).

Figure 1: BAMs allocation strategy

The resource allocation strategy used by bandwidth allocation models makes use of three types of resource allocation (Figure 1):

1. Private Resource (Private) – In this alternative for resource allocation, the resource is exclusive of a Traffic Class (TC);
2. Sharing "high to low" (high-to-low - HTL)[†] – In this alternative, the bandwidth allocated to higher priority TCs and not in use can be temporarily allocated to TCs with lower priority; and
3. Sharing "low to high" (low-to-high - LTH)[‡] – In this alternative, the bandwidth allocated to lower priority TCs and not in use can be temporary allocated as loans to higher TCs priority.

The Maximum Allocation Model (MAM) is presented in Le Faucheur (2005c) and Tong (2007) and, in this model, each traffic class (TC) is configured by the network administrator to use a certain amount of link bandwidth (resource). This resource is allocated on demand to applications belonging to the traffic classes (TCs).

The MAM effectively isolates traffic classes (TC) and there isn't sharing of bandwidth between applications belonging to different classes. As shown in Figure 1, it can be stated that MAM only uses the strategy of allocating private resources.

The Russian Dolls Model (RDM) is presented in Le Faucheur (2005a) and Pinto Neto (2008) and, in this model, TCs with the highest values are hierarchically superior to TCs with lower values (priority scheme). The general reasoning involved in the operation of the RDM model is derived from the basic model of priorities used by network applications. In this case, the bandwidth not used by higher priority applications may be temporarily used by lower priority applications.

The RDM is an effective evolution of the MAM model and introduced the first attempt to share resources between TCs and hence LSPs. In effect, the RDM allows the sharing of high-priority applications unused bandwidth by low priority applications. According to previous classification for main resource allocation strategies, the RDM model uses only high-to-low (HTL) sharing.

The G-RDM model is basically a hybrid model combining allocation strategies "high to low" from RDM proposal with private resources strategy proposed by MAM (Le Faucheur, 2005c). The overall operation result is a hybrid model MAM / RDM with a limited amount of resource sharing for applications allocated to different traffic classes.

The AllocTC-Sharing model uses an opportunistic strategy for allocating resources (bandwidth) (Reale, 2012). AllocTC-Sharing allows two resource allocation strategies simultaneously: sharing high-to-low (HTL) and sharing low-to-high (LTH). The "high-to-low" allocation style is equivalent to the RDM model. The "low-to-high" bandwidth allocation style allows high priority classes temporarily allocate unused bandwidth reserved mainly for low priority classes in the form of loans.

BAM Characteristics	Operational	MAM	RDM	AllocTC-Sharing
Sharing from "high to low"		No	Yes	Yes
Sharing from "low to high"		No	No	Yes
Bandwidth utilization with high volume of traffic (low priority)		Low	High	High
Bandwidth utilization with high volume of traffic (high priority)		Low	low	High
Isolation between TCs		High	Medium	Low

Table 1: BAMs operating characteristics (MAM, RDM and ALLOCTC -SHARING)

[†] In this strategy, one considers the "preemption" less priority applications for priority applications where there is a need for bandwidth by priority applications.

[‡] In this strategy, the concept of "loan" is the temporary use of bandwidth allocated to lower priority TCs by priority LSPs. "Devolution" is the premature closure of a priority LSP established by loan.

3 Bandwidth Constraints Reconfigurations Analysis

Computer networks are mostly dynamic, asymmetric, and multipath and typically have limited resources in terms of bandwidth. Bandwidth Allocation Models focus on resource utilization but, when managed individually, have a static behavior that is accordance with the dynamic, multi-path and asymmetric behavior of most networks. As such it is expected that different BAMs could be used depending on the traffic profile currently applied to the network.

In this section, we address design issues in order to support on-the-fly reconfiguration of BCs and operating results for two management strategies: Soft and Hard Approaches.

The MAM model admits no bandwidth sharing between traffic classes (TC) (neither "high-to-low" nor "low-to-high") and, as such, does not implement any preemption mechanism.

Considering MAM, if a traffic class (TC) has available bandwidth and the manager wants to assign it to another TC, there is no design and/or operational impact. It is just a management decision. The reconfiguration process, in turn, may consider distinct approaches:

1. MAM reconfiguration with Soft Approach (SA) – in this case, it should be necessary to create a monitoring mechanism in order to track LSPs setup and closure in order to keep track of the bandwidth constraints and availability. Based on this information, the reconfiguration management process could be executed smoothly and preserve established LSPs.
2. MAM reconfiguration with Hard Approach – in this case, LSPs could be preempted abruptly in order to reconfigure the network to a new set of bandwidth constraint.

In both solutions it is required an implementation effort (monitoring and LSP preemption) in order to implement the adopted management approach. It is important to notice that the HA effectively contradicts the MAM basic premise of reserving bandwidth for applications.

The RDM model allows low-priority applications to benefit from available bandwidth not allocated by high priority applications. In this model existing available bandwidth in TCs that will reduce the size of BC will not have any operational impact.

In RDM, low saturated TCs may reduce their BC bandwidth on behalf of other TCs by using a preemption mechanism in order to make the necessary adjustments (eventual LSP teardown). It is necessary in this case to verify that the internal implementation of the algorithms counters is updated consistently. The main reconfiguration problem occurs when we need to reconfigure a high priority saturated TC in order to assign bandwidth for a low priority TC. In this situation we may have the following management approaches:

1. RDM reconfiguration with Soft Approach – in this case, it is necessary to create a monitoring mechanism in order to keep track of LSPs setup and teardown. A bandwidth availability control is necessary to guarantee any smooth reconfiguration.
2. RDM reconfiguration with Hard Approach – in this case, the existing preemption mechanism can be used to terminate established LSP belonging to the saturated high priority TC. For all preempted LSPs the bandwidth constraint is adjusted and reconfigured.

The hard reconfiguration approach will effectively hurt the RDM model by allowing a low priority LSP force a teardown of high priority LSP. The soft reconfiguration approach, in turn, will smoothly depend on LSPs teardown closing time.

It is important to note that the RDM model reconfiguration differs from the MAM since it only occurs when we need to reduce the bandwidth configured for BC (bandwidth constraints) of a saturated high priority TC.

The AllocTC-Sharing model supports both styles of sharing concomitantly: "high-to-low" and "low-to-high". The AllocTC-sharing enables the use of available bandwidth in both directions. Thus, the AllocTC-sharing model implementation has mechanisms for preemption "high-to-low" and devolution (Preemption "low to high"). In terms of reconfiguration, there are the following approaches for AllocTC-Sharing:

1. AllocTC-Sharing reconfiguration with Hard Approach – In this case, it is not necessary any additional implementation. It is only necessary to check the implementation of the internal counters to ensure bandwidth consistency after reconfiguration of BCs.
2. AllocTC-Sharing reconfiguration with Soft Approach – In this case, it is necessary to create a monitoring and control mechanism in order to keep track of LSPs setup and teardown and to adjust bandwidth constraint availability.

As an operational effect of the reconfiguration with Hard Approach, we can have a high priority LSP being teardown or being counted as a lower loan TC and, as such, it loses its intrinsic priority with reconfiguration.

In summary, the management of bandwidth constraints reconfiguration for allocation models MAM, RDM and AllocTC-Sharing occurs transparently when available TC bandwidth is transferred among TCs regardless of its priority. Major BAM reconfiguration issues can occur when a saturated TC is required to provide extra bandwidth to any other TC.

In the three allocation models evaluated (MAM, RDM and AllocTC-Sharing), the reconfiguration with Hard Approach may imply in unwanted operating results which corresponds in effect to have LSPs being abruptly teardown. In MAM and RDM models, the reconfiguration with Hard Approach requires additional implementation (monitoring and control preemption facility) in relation to models actual implementation.

The reconfiguration with Soft Approach requires a management plan to coordinate the reconfiguration. This plan makes adjustments gradually observing the teardown of LSPs that release resources (bandwidth). The operational effects of this approach point to a better preservation of the operational characteristics of the BAMs, but need some execution time in order to converge to a new reconfiguration pattern of the BAM considered.

We argue that the two approaches (HA and SA) are important for most networks (having distinct traffic profiles) and should be implemented in order to guarantee the choice between them is a managerial issue.

In the following section, it will be presented the evaluation of the Hard Approach vs. the Soft Approach for the RDM model using a traffic scenario where a saturated high priority TC needs to be reconfigured in order to release bandwidth for a of lower priority TC (worst case).

4 BAM Reconfiguration - Evaluation and Analysis

In this section, BAM reconfiguration is evaluated with the main objective of exemplifying and validating different operational behaviors discussed for the reconfiguration with Hard Approach and Reconfiguration with Soft Approach.

In terms of evaluation scenario, the RDM model was chosen since it is largely referenced in the literature and also because it's operational behavior can be mapped to other models.

The network topology used intends to demonstrate the discussed limiting traffic scenarios and included a traffic source (S1) and a destination (D) interconnected through a link of 622 Mbps with two classes of traffic (Figure 2.): TC0 - low priority applications and TC1 - high priority applications.

Figure 2: Network Topology used in the simulation

In terms of the simulation, we force the saturation of the network by making LSPs setups to exceed I number LSPs teardowns. As such, simulation will lead to a scenario of high saturation and competition between TCs:

1. LSPs arrival requests: modeled exponentially with a mean of 2 s;
2. LSPs duration: modeled exponentially - average of 250 seconds, causing saturation of the link;
3. LSP band: evenly distributed between 5 Mbps and 15 Mbps;
4. Stop Criteria - 1000 LSPs.

Bandwidth Constraints (BCs) are reconfigured in three phases (Table 2):

1. In the first phase, simulation starts with high priority LSPs (TC1) BC1 set to 60% of the link (372.20 Mbps) and the network is saturated and stabilized with this configuration.
2. In the second phase, simulation starts with the network saturated and after 450 LSPs being created, BC1 is reduced by 20% leading to a TC1 available bandwidth of 248.8 Mbps (40%).
3. Finally in phase 3, after 650 LSPs the simulation further reduces BC1 in 20% reducing TC1 available bandwidth to 124.4 Mbps (20%).

BC	Max BC(%)	Max BC	BC
Phase 1			
BC0	100	622,0	TC0+TC1
BC1	60	373,2	TC1
Phase 2			
BC0	100	622,0	TC0+TC1
BC1	40	248,8	TC1
Phase 3			
BC0	100	622,0	TC0+TC1
BC1	20	124,4	TC1

Table 2: Simulation phases - bandwidth constraints (BCs) by traffic class (TC)

The overall scenario was simulated with 05 random seeds and the results are presented as the mean value obtained (confidence interval 95%) (Macdougall, 1987).

The parameters evaluated in the simulation were: link utilization (by TC and link), preemptions and LSP blocking.

5 Simulated Characteristics of RDM (BAM) Reconfiguration

The main difference between the Hard and the Soft management approaches is reflected in the number of preemptions resulting from RDM reconfigurations. As can be seen in Figure 3, when the Hard Approach is adopted, the number of preemptions increases significantly reconfiguration simulated by phase changes. This is due to the fact that LSPs that exceed TC1 BC are terminated immediately (abruptly). The Soft Approach leads to a smoother operational behavior of the network

and results in having a significantly smaller number of preemptions for TC1 (Figure 5). TC0 behavior is conventional or, in other words, RDM-like (Figure 4).

Figure 3: Number of Preemptions (total)

Figure 4: Number of Preemptions in TC0 and TC1

Figure 5 illustrates link utilization behavior for HA and SA reconfiguration. Link utilization effectively declines for a short period in the HA phase. These negative picks are due to the sudden teardown of LSPs in order allocate bandwidth among BCs. This impact is not observed in Soft Approach since it waits for the termination of LSPs gradually before adjusting BCs configuration.

Figure 5: Link utilization

Figure 6 illustrates link load by TCs. The reconfiguration with Hard Approach immediately reallocates TC0 bandwidth for all phases. It can also be observed the immediate drop in TC1 use and TC0 immediate growth. In the reconfiguration with Soft Approach, the bandwidth availability for TC1 and TC0 is adjusted gradually.

Figure 6: Link load in TC0 and TC1

Table 3 presents a summary of preemptions, blocking and link utilization for SA and HA reconfiguration approaches. In general, the Hard Approach results in a greater number of preemptions for TC1 but, in turn, results in a smaller number of blockings and greater average link utilization.

The reconfiguration Soft Approach respects the intrinsic priority of the LSPs (TC1) by waiting LSPs teardown. The number of preemptions is reduced and is slightly greater.

	Soft Approach			Hard Approach		
	TC0	TC1	Total	TC0	TC1	Total
Preemptions	46	0	46	49	29	78
Blocking	247	366	613	239	351	590
LSPs setup	-	-	2349	-	-	2266
Average Link Utilization	490	121	611	494	121	615

Table 3: SA and HA – preemptions, blocking and link utilization

6 Final Considerations

Network managers may adopt different BAMs as a possible management response to changes in their network traffic profile. As discussed in section III of this paper, distinct BAMs allocation behaviors will lead to different traffic allocation patterns with distinct operational parameters such as preemption, link utilization and LSP (flow) blocking. Considering then that managers will have to switching among BAMs, this paper has analyzed and evaluated the impact of these parameters (behavior) during BAMs reconfiguration process.

It was assumed two possible management approaches in order to facilitate the analyses of the network parameters behavior. In general, it was indicated that the reconfiguration process with Hard Approach, necessary in networks needing rapid response to network traffic changes will potentially impact applications by increasing the number of preemptions.

In turn, the reconfiguration process with Soft Approach leads to a smoother impact in terms of preemptions and does maintain the normal characteristics of the BAM. SA main drawback is the required convergence time that is directly dependent on the LSP teardown procedure.

Both reconfiguration approaches do require an additional level of intervention in the network beyond the BAM implementation itself (monitoring and action facilities).

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